

DURABILITY OF EPOXY ADHESIVES USED TO BOND CFRP LAMINATES TO CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY

An experimental program was undertaken to evaluate the durability of three commercial epoxy adhesives used for bonding repairing and strengthening Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) to concrete structures. The changes in physical and mechanical properties after exposure for up to 18 months under different environmental conditions are reported and discussed.

Keywords: rehabilitation, concrete, epoxy, adhesives, CFRP, durability

INTRODUCTION

The repair and strengthening of deteriorated, damaged and old concrete infrastructures has become an important challenge for civil engineers worldwide [1]. One of the techniques used in the rehabilitation of those structures is the external bonding of CFRP laminates by employing epoxy resin adhesives [2, 3].

In such applications, the applied materials are exposed to outdoor environmental conditions, including humidity, rain, saline and ground water and, also, highly alkaline solutions originated by the chemical composition of the concrete itself [4]. Thus, it is of great interest an assessment of the durability of the materials involved in such applications - epoxy adhesives and CFRP laminates, but also the integrity of the system as a whole.

This work is part of a larger research project which aims at predicting the long-term behaviour of several commercial CFRP laminate/adhesive systems used in the rehabilitation of concrete structures [5]. In the overall project it was recognized that the durability of this rehabilitation solution depends, extensively on the performance of the adhesives used for the bonding of the CFRP laminates to concrete. The present document brings into focus the part of the investigation concerning the durability of the epoxy adhesives used to bond CFRP to concrete.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The three commercial epoxy adhesives selected to be studied are identified along the present text as A, B and C. Test specimens were manufactured in appropriate moulds, with the dimensions required for the type of test chosen, to assess the adhesives properties after exposure to the several ageing conditions. The cure of the test specimens was carried out at room temperature, for one month.

Characterization of adhesives was extensively performed by using different techniques, such as chemical (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy-FTIR, Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy - EDX), thermal (Thermogravimetry - TG, Dynamic Mechanical Analysis - DMA), mechanical, as well as morphology observation by microscopy (Scanning Electronic Microscopy - SEM). The obtained results are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1: Physical-chemical properties of adhesives

Property	Method	Adhesive A	Adhesive B	Adhesive C
Chemical composition	FTIR	Two components epoxy material based on DGEBA with aliphatic amines, as hardener		
Filler content	TG	88 %	60 %	55 %
Filler nature	EDX	Calcium carbonate Silicates	Silicates	Calcium carbonate Silicates
Relative density	Hydrostatic weighing	1.87	1.55	1.61
T_g [$E'_{initial} / \tan \delta$]	DMA	56.7 / 71.2 °C	34.9 / 47.9 °C	61.5 / 76.7 °C
Mechanical properties	Tension	$\sigma_t = 26.4$ MPa $E_t = 9.20$ GPa	$\sigma_t = 7.2$ MPa $E_t = 0.86$ GPa	$\sigma_t = 24.3$ MPa $E_t = 4.61$ GPa
	Flexural	$\sigma_f = 53.1$ MPa $E_f = 9.19$ GPa	$\sigma_f = 18.2$ MPa $E_f = 1.84$ GPa	$\sigma_f = 60.0$ MPa $E_f = 7.22$ GPa

Figure 1: Adhesives morphology of upper surface and transversal sections (SEM)

Methods

In order to investigate the environmental effects on epoxy adhesives, they were exposed to the ageing conditions described in Table 2. Since adhesives used to bond CFRP to concrete can be exposed to saline (from sea water) and alkaline (from concrete pore water) solutions, it was assessed the effect of these solutions on the adhesives, in addition to the immersion in water. Temperatures of 40 °C and 60 °C were used to accelerate the degradation mechanisms. In addition, a hygrothermal ageing was performed under a hot-wet environment.

Table 2: Aging conditions

Type of exposure	Duration	Conditions
Continuous condensation (CC-40)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Temperature: 40 (± 2) °C ▪ Relative humidity: 100 %
Immersion in demineralised water (IW-23), (IW-40), (IW-60)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Temperatures: 23 (± 2) °C, 40 (± 1) °C and 60 (± 1) °C
Immersion in salt-water (IS-23), (IS-40), (IS-60)	18 months	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Composition: 35 g/l NaCl ▪ Temperatures: 23 (± 2) °C, 40 (± 1) °C and 60 (± 1) °C
Immersion in alkaline solution (IL-23), (IL-40), (IL-60)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Composition: 118 g/l Ca(OH)₂, 4 g/l KOH and 0,9 g/l NaOH ▪ Temperatures: 23 (± 2) °C, 40 (± 1) °C and 60 (± 1) °C

After exposure to the conditions presented in Table 2, aged test specimens of each epoxy adhesives were subjected to the following tests:

- (i) Mass changes: Controlled specimens (with the same geometry of flexural test specimens) were periodically removed from the exposure and weighted.
- (ii) Tensile testing: Tests were conducted according to ISO 527 – parts 1 and 2 [6] in epoxy adhesive specimens using the type 1 test specimens (dog-bone geometry), in an *Instron 4483* universal mechanical testing machine. The loading rate was 1 mm/min. At least five replicates were tested for each adhesive and ageing condition.
- (iii) Flexural testing: Three point bending flexural tests were conducted according to ISO 178 [7] in epoxy adhesive specimens with a span-to-depth ratio of 16, in the above referred universal mechanical testing machine . The loading rate was 2 mm/min. At least five replicates were tested for each adhesive and ageing condition.
- (iv) Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA): DMA has been used to analyze the viscoelastic response of adhesives and to assess the glass transition temperature (T_g), in accordance with ISO 6721 [8]. Dual cantilever type clamp specimens were tested, in a *TA Q800* equipment, at a constant frequency of 1 Hz and strain amplitude of 15 μ m. The analysis was carried out from room temperature to 150 °C, at a rate of 2 °C/min.

RESULTS

Mass changes

Figure 2 illustrates the mass variation measured over different immersion ageing (water, saline and alkaline solution) and temperature conditions (23 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C), as well as continuous condensation at 40 °C, for the three adhesives.

As can be seen, the mass variation is dependent of the immersion media and temperature, for all adhesives. In particular, and for each ageing, it was observed the following behaviour:

(i) Immersion in water

Adhesives A and C show a maximum level of mass variation at the higher immersion temperature, as expected. Those results are consistent with others described for different types of epoxy adhesives [9]. This could be explained by two kind of reasons: on one hand, the higher temperature can lead to morphological changes, like crack formation, that promote the ingress of a larger amount of water into the material – this option was excluded after observation of the test specimens, by SEM; on the other hand, considering that temperature speeds up the diffusion process, it could be expected that the raised temperatures quickly leads to the saturation level – at a lower temperature the process takes more time. Adhesive B, despite having an increased mass at room temperature, shows a decrease of mass after an initial increment, when immersed at the higher temperatures. This fact may be related with the incomplete degree of cure of this adhesive, that favours the leaching of some un-reacted soluble components in water. FTIR analysis of the immersion media revealed the presence of organic material, proving this assumption (Figure 3).

(ii) Immersion in saline solution

For all adhesives a lower variation of mass in salt-water was verified, when compared with the immersion in water at the same temperature.

(iii) Immersion in alkaline solution

All adhesives test specimens presented larger mass variations, particularly at the higher temperature. It was noticed, however, that those variations were increased due to the deposition of salts on the test specimen surfaces. SEM observation of those surfaces revealed superficial crack formation, due to chemical attack.

Figure 2: Mass variation of adhesives over different ageing conditions

(iv) Continuous condensation at 40 °C: For all adhesives, the mass variation observed was higher than the obtained after immersion in water at the same temperature. Since SEM observations showed no outward cracks, this difference can be explained by a chemical reaction of adhesives under the saturated air condition that was inhibited in water immersion conditions.

Figure 3: FTIR spectra of water after immersion of adhesive B at 40 °C and 60 °C

Tensile and flexural properties

The tensile and flexural properties (mean value \pm standard deviation) determined in adhesives after different ageing conditions are plotted in Figure 4. In those graphics, the strength (in MPa) and modulus (in GPa) are represented by bars and single squares, respectively. It was impossible to perform tensile tests after ageing in alkaline solution at the higher temperature conditions, because the material became very fragile.

It was also observed that adhesive B showed a much lower tensile and flexural strength, as well as modulus, when compared with the other two types of adhesives. This fact can be mainly attributed to their under cured status, as it was demonstrated by dynamic mechanical analysis.

The mechanical behaviour of adhesives after ageing, evaluated by determination of tensile and flexural properties, presented distinct performances:

- (i) An overall decrease in properties of adhesive A was observed in all immersion conditions; in addition, for this adhesive, higher temperatures caused further degradation. Alkaline immersion was the most aggressive condition. After 18 months of immersion in that solution at 40 °C, this adhesive presented tensile and flexural strength retentions of 14% and 22%, respectively.
- (ii) For adhesive B, it was impossible to make a correct evaluation of the degradation of its mechanical properties due to its incomplete cure. In fact, the post-cure occurred during ageing hides any reduction of properties caused by eventual degradation mechanisms that could arise, in parallel.
- (iii) In general, adhesive C was the most resistant to the different ageing conditions. However, for the most aggressive condition – immersion in alkaline solution at 60°C – the flexural strength retention was 37%.

Figure 4: Tensile and flexural properties for adhesives, before and after different ageing conditions (strength and modulus represented by bars and single squares, respectively)

Overall, the immersion in the saline solution caused minor effects, whereas the immersion in alkaline solution had the greatest degradation outcome. Furthermore, temperature, as a speed up factor, amplifies the degradation caused by the different immersion conditions.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Figure 5 shows the experimental dynamic mechanical curves for adhesives A, B and C, after submission to the different ageing conditions (for each condition, only one curve corresponding to a typical specimen is shown). On the left, plots show changes in dynamic storage modulus (E') with temperature, for the different exposure conditions; the corresponding $\tan \delta$ curves are shown on the right.

The dynamic mechanical analysis performed on adhesives A and C, after different ageing conditions, showed a general reduction of T_g values, not systematically followed by reduction in material stiffness. The reduction of the intensity of $\tan \delta$ curve peak and the widening of its base suggests that the ageing of these two adhesives involves a plasticization mechanism [10]. The sprouting of a shoulder in the experimental curve around 100 °C suggests the presence of water in the hygrothermally aged specimens, as

described elsewhere [11]. For adhesive B it is seen that the peak of $\tan \delta$ curve moves to a higher temperature revealing the progression of the cure over time. It is also noted, as expected, that the glassy storage modulus increases.

Figure 5: DMA experimental curves for adhesives, after different ageing conditions

CONCLUSIONS

The changes in physical and mechanical properties after exposure up to 18 months under different environmental conditions - immersion in demineralised water, salt and alkaline solutions at room temperature (23°C), 40°C and 60°C, as well as under constant-humidity condensation atmosphere at 40°C - are reported and discussed.

The experimental results showed that the adhesives composition and their state of cure may strongly influence the performance of those materials in different ageing environments. Particularly, in the case of adhesives used in field applications under uncontrolled and different ambient conditions, like those studied in this work, it was possible to find materials with very distinct properties and sensitivities for the environmental factors.

Since the efficiency of strengthening of concrete structures by external bonding of CFRP laminates depends on the durability of the adhesive, the results obtained offer valuable information which can be used, not only to characterize the behaviour of epoxy adhesives, but also for a better understanding of the degradation mechanisms involved which are the basis for the design of service life-prediction models.

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